

GENDER ANALYSIS OF MELON PRODUCTION IN IBARAPA AREAS OF OYO STATE, NIGERIA.

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Abstract

*This study investigated the roles of men and women in the production of melon, *Colosynthis citrullus* a popular vegetable crop in Nigeria. A purposive random sampling process was used to select 120 melon farmers from the study area and data were taken using interview schedule. The data collected were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The result showed that men (68%) and women (32%) were actively involved in melon production, out of which 81% (men) and 22% (women) were fully involved in the production activities. Such activities as land clearing, planting, pod breaking, and seed washing were almost exclusive roles of men while seed selection, seed extraction and drying and cleaning were women's roles. The *t*-test also showed that there is significant difference ($t_c=17.65$, $t_r=2.35$) in the level of involvement of men and women in melon production. The study recommends that adequate recognition be given to both men and women on crop production incentives.*

Introduction

A larger proportion of the rural people, (men and women) are involved in the cultivation of food crops on subsistence and medium scale levels. More than 70% of

the population in developing nations especially in Africa depend directly on agriculture as a means of livelihood, (Buckland, 1996).

Over the decades, the roles of women in the agricultural sector have not been clearly defined. It is widely believed that men are farmers while women supply family labour by helping their husbands on the farm. The production decisions are mostly taken by men according to the right they possess over women who are customarily expected to engage in food crop production for family consumption. Gbadamosi (1989) stated that women in Nigeria engage in a wide range of farming activities and are responsible in most cases for food production, processing and distribution for home consumption and for sale. For this reason, men were usually the target for agricultural development because there had been the concentration of production factors in the hands of men than the women.

The social science defines "gender" as the roles and activities of men and women. These roles are often expressed by the traditions and beliefs of a particular culture. However, in the traditional African society, women are considered as economically inactive, not contributing to the family income, they only work only as unpaid family labour, taking care of children, food preparation and processing. Their contribution to the creation of form utility to farm produce for marketing is not adequately recognised. According to Yahaya (2002), women do help their husbands on the farm in almost all the farm operations ranging from planting and harvesting to processing of crops. With this, men and women can be said to complement one another in the production process.

According to Fawole (1995), agricultural production is characterised by sexual division of labour in which both men and women complement one another.

Gender responsibility in agriculture could be seen from different patterns according to Gbadebo (2001) and Feldstain (1989). They include:

- a. **Separate Enterprise** where men and women specialize in different crop production within the household system. Here, men and women do not produce the same crop.
- b. **Separate Field** where women produce the same crop on the farm as men do, but women's production is majorly on a subsistent base, while that of men can be on a large scale.
- c. **Share Task** in this pattern, men and women share the tasks on the farm. Both men and women have their own plots and all perform the operations together except in some labour intensive tasks when men alone perform.

- d. **Separate Task** this embraces men and women doing separate jobs, since women are termed weaker sex, they are often given less tedious jobs like harvesting, planting, sorting and storage.

In order to have a meaningful development in agriculture, concerted efforts should be made to utilize the potentials of men and women. In this investigation, a few research questions become pertinent, such as;

- What are the personal characteristics of melon farmers in the study area?
- What are the level of involvement of men and women in the production of melon crop in the study area?
- What specific activities do the men and women perform in the production of melon in the study area?

The general objective of the study is to evaluate gender roles in melon production in Ibarapa area of Oyo State and specifically to:

- identify the social and personal characteristics of melon farmers;
- assess the levels of involvement of men and women in melon production;
- identify the roles of men and women in melon production in the study area.

Methodology

The area of study:

The study was conducted in Ibarapa area of Oyo State, Nigeria. The area is made up of Ibarapa Central, East and North Local Governments of the State.

The choice of the area for this study was due to several reasons particularly, the prevalence of rural characteristics and the predominance of melon crop production which is a result of favourable soil and climatic factors that favour the production of the crop. Ibarapa area of Oyo State consists of predominantly an agrarian population. The people engage in the cultivation of a wide range of crops on a small and medium scale levels in addition to other agricultural activities. Women involvement in farming activities is quite pronounced. The bulk of agricultural production centres on manually cultivated rain fed crops. The crops grown include

arable crops such as maize, guinea corn, yam, cowpea, cassava, sugarcane, rice, melons, leaf vegetables and cash crops such as cocoa, cashew, oranges, mango, oil-palm, etc.

Furthermore, due to the geographical location of the area, there are two main cropping seasons, early planting season, commencing around March to April and late planting season commencing around July to August. This pattern allows for the cultivation of melon crop twice in a year by the farmers. However, inter-cropping is a prevalent practice throughout the entire study area.

Sampling procedure and sample size:

The target population of this study consisted of melon farmers in the three Local Government areas that make up Ibarapa in Oyo State. Multi-stage and purposive sampling techniques were used to select respondents for the study. They consist of male farmers and their female counterparts. On the whole, 120 melon farmers were selected in the entire study area.

Study variables:

These are the levels of involvement of men and women in melon production based on responses provided by the respondents, the roles of men and women in melon production determined as the percentage of the activities performed by men and women respectively.

The research instrument used in this study was a comprehensive interview schedule. It consists of both open and close ended questions related to the objectives of the study. The instrument consists of questions related to the levels of involvement and the roles of men and women in the production of melon. The interview schedules were administered to respondents in their homes and villages.

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Results and discussion

Selected Social and Personal Characteristics of Melon Farmers

Table 1: Distribution of respondents according to personal information data.

Variables		Frequency	Percentage
A	Age: 26-35years	8	7
	36-45years	36	30
	46-55years	44	36
	56-65years	27	23
	>65years	5	4
	Total	120	100
B	Gender: Male	81	68
	Female	39	32
	Total	120	100
C	Marital status: Single	9	7.5
	Married	101	84
	Widowed	9	7.5
	Divorced	1	1
	Total	120	100
D	Educational level:		
	No formal education	15	12.5
	Informal education	16	13
	Primary education	21	17.5
	Secondary & tertiary educ.	68	57
Total	120	100	
E	Production experience:		
	2-5years	33	28
	6-10years	38	32
	11-15years	22	18
	16-20years	11	9
	21-25years	7	6
	26years & above	9	8
Total	120	100	

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Table 1 shows that melon farmers in the area consist of 68% male and 32% females. These are made up of the married (84%), single (8%), widowed (7%), and 1% divorced. A larger proportion, (75%) of melon farmers in the area have one form of formal education or the other with only 25% not attending any form of formal education. Of the 120 respondents, 13% are illiterate and 12% have informal education. The literate farmers among them consist of those with primary education 18%, secondary education and above 57%, consisting of civil servants, pensioners and traders that are actively involved in melon farming.

The experience of the farmers show that 28% of the farmers have been producing melon for between 2-5 years while another 32% have being into melon production for between 6-10 years. The percentages of farmers with 11-15 years, 16-20 years and above 20 years of experience in melon production are 18%, 9% and 13% respectively.

Men and Women Involvement in Melon Production

Table 2: Distribution of respondents on their levels of involvement in melon production

Level of Involvement	Male		Female	
	F	%	F	%
Fully involved	66	81.5	8	22
Partially involved	14	17.3	29	75
Never involved	1	1.2	2	3
Total	81	100	39	100

Table 2 shows that majority of the respondents (81%) of the male respondents are fully involved in melon production activities while 22% of the females are fully involved in melon production activities. These are the categories that have their personal farmlands cropped with melon and actually take lead roles in the cultivation and processing of melon to obtain edible seeds.

The percentage of the respondents that is partially involved in melon production among men is about 18% while those of the women respondents were 75% of the total women sampled. This category was discovered to be those that

engage hired labour for almost every activity of melon production from land clearing to sun-drying of the seeds, and only perform the cleaning and bagging of dried melon seeds.

The test of the relationship between the personal data of the respondents and levels of involvement in melon production showed that there is no significant relationship ($r=2.71, p=16.71$) between sex and age of respondents and their levels of involvement in melon production, while a significant relationship ($r=0.685, p=0.000$) exists between educational level of respondents and their levels of involvement in melon production.

The roles of Men and Women in Melon Production

Table 3: Percentage of activities performed by respondents in melon production

Activities	100% Male	100% Female	100% Total
Land clearing	78	22	100
Land preparation	73	27	100
Seed selection	26	74	100
Planting	71	29	100
Weeding	65	35	100
Fertilizer application	6	94	100
Pod gathering	12	88	100
Pod breaking	77	23	100
Seed extraction	15	85	100
Washing	75	25	100
Sun-drying	65	35	100
Bagging	41	59	100

The production activities involved in melon production include the following; land clearing, land preparation, seed selection, planting, weeding, fertilizer application, pod gathering, breaking of melon pods, seed extraction, washing, seed drying, cleaning and bagging.

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Each of these activities is performed by both sexes but at different levels. For land clearing operation, it is performed by about 78% of men while only 22% of women perform the operation. Also, 73% of men perform land preparation while 27% of women perform land preparation. Seed selection for planting is considered to be chiefly a women affair as it is performed by 74% women while only 26% of men perform the activity. The planting operation is performed by 71 % of men while 29% of women perform the same operation, and this was explained to be based on the hectareage of farmland. Timely weeding of melon farm is very important, and this is performed by 65% men and 35% women respectively. Fertilizer application on melon farms is not a common practice in the study area, thus a small proportion of male respondents (7%) do perform fertilizer application on melon farms while a very large proportion (94%) of women engage in the operation.

The drying up and withering of melon vines indicates the readiness of melon fruits for harvesting, and the process is termed pod gathering. This activity is majorly performed by women (88%) and 12% men. Conversely, the pod breaking operation is mainly performed by men (77%) while 23% of women perform the operation. This is due to the traditional method of breaking melon pods involving the use of clubs and high strength. The broken pods after a period of fermentation are ripped of their seed content, and this operation is majorly performed by women (85%) with only about 15% of men performing the operation.

The washing of extracted seeds is done at a flowing stream and the operation is mostly performed by men (75%) while about 25% of women also do the washing of melon seeds. In the same vein, drying of melon seeds is done by men (65%) while 35% women engage in the operation. However, cleaning (winnowing) of dried melon seeds is most commonly performed by women (86%) with only about 19% of men engaging in the operation.

The t-test analysis of the levels of involvement of men and women in melon production activities shows a significant difference ($p=2.358$, $t=17.65$) in the levels of involvement of both sexes. The significant difference observed was discovered during the interview process to be due to the specific energy demand of some of the activities involved in melon production.

Conclusion and Recommendations

From the results, it could be concluded that melon crop is produced by both men and women farmers, and both sexes are actively involved in the production and processing activities. The roles performed however depend on the sex.

Consequently, it recommended that policies geared towards improving the production capacities of farmers should bear in mind the contributions of the women along-side those of men. Also, students in schools and colleges should be involved in the cultivation of melon to increase national output.

Introduction

Philosophy is a subject which deals with some of the most general questions about the universe and our place in it. It is quite different from science, because its questions cannot be answered empirically by observation or experiment, but its purpose is entirely intellectual. The first Islamic philosopher to emerge among the

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